

General Semantic Annotation GeMTeX Annotation Guideline

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1 Introduction and Motivation

In everyday clinical practice, a large number of texts are still created and managed. Since texts are considered *unstructured data*, the statistical analysis or further processing of the data they contain is extremely labor-intensive.

The research field concerned with this problem is called *computational linguistics* or also *Natural Language Processing* (NLP) and focuses on the automatic processing of natural language. Methods in this research field range from rule-based neurosymbolic approaches to machine learning. Suitable training data are needed for the development and evaluation of these methods in the clinical context, especially in the German-speaking area.

For this purpose, the project **GeMTeX**¹ (German Medical Text Corpus) was launched as part of the Medical Informatics Initiative (MII). The aim of the project is to enrich clinical texts from routine care with metadata and make them available for research. Numerous research institutions and university hospitals from all over Germany are involved in the project. Six university hospitals are annotating sites: Charité in Berlin, University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus Dresden, University Hospital Erlangen, University Hospital Essen, University Hospital Leipzig and TUM Klinikum München. Each of these six sites extracts and annotates a few thousand clinical documents according to the same guidelines. In this way, a varied collection of diverse clinical documents is to be created, representing German clinical language with diverse medical backgrounds and high variance in formulation, disease courses, and other characteristics.

The basis for the annotation of the clinical documents is the currently latest full version of the English-language International Edition of the most comprehensive clinical ontology-based terminology SNOMED CT². With the help of SNOMED CT, text spans in the GeMTeX texts are directly *grounded*, that is, assigned a standardized meaning. For example, the word *Tilidin* is assigned the SNOMED CT concept “SCTID: 373562008 | Tilidine (substance)” and can be directly retrieved again. Relations are then drawn between semantically intertwined concepts³.

The practical implementation of semantic annotation takes place primarily in the annotation tool *INCEpTION*⁴⁵. The annotators receive real clinical documents with patient references that have been machine-preannotated by Averbis Health Discovery⁶ and previously de-identified. A recommender system by ID Logik suggests alternative SNOMED CT concepts for each annotated text span. Depending on the quality of the preannotations, the annotators must correct or delete them and search the text for spans that were not recognized. To identify the correct SNOMED CT concept, it is recommended to use the SNOMED CT International SNOMED CT Browser⁷ via the web browser for access to the English-language International Edition.

¹<https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/de/gemtex-medizinische-texte-fuer-die-forschung-automatisiert-erschliessen>

²https://www.bfarm.de/DE/Kodiersysteme/Terminologien/SNOMEDCT-CT/_node.html

³Important: The relations inherent to SNOMED CT are **not** annotated (see Section 5).

⁴<https://inception-project.github.io>

⁵More detailed information on INCEpTION can be found in the GeMTeX De-Identification Guide: <https://zenodo.org/records/11502329>

⁶<https://averbis.com/health-discovery/>

⁷<https://browser.ihtsdotools.org/>

2 Definitions and Annotation Maxims

2.1 Definitions

Term	Definition
Adjacency	Direct neighborhood of two units (e.g. two tokens or SNOMED CT concepts).
Ambiguity	A linguistic ambiguity that cannot be resolved, or can only be resolved, through contextual or background knowledge.
Anaphor	A backward-referring linguistic element within a text.
Annotate	A text span provided with a SNOMED CT Concept ID or a SNOMED CT concept.
(Semantic) Domain	<i>Technical-formal:</i> The set of all concepts permitted for annotation. <i>Pragmatic:</i> In principle, all SNOMED CT concepts with the exception of concepts under “SCTID: 243796009 Situation with explicit context (situation)”. However, the concept groups highlighted in this guideline should be focused on.
Factuality	Factuality describes the truth value of statements. Trigger words, such as e.g. “presumably”, are often responsible for a modified truth value of a statement.
Coordination	Syntactic phenomenon where two or more linguistic units are separated by a conjunction or list elements, but fulfill the same syntactic function.
Coordinated units	Linguistic units that are subject to the syntactic phenomenon of “coordination”.
Coordination predicate	A text span that refers structurally and semantically to coordinated units or defines them more precisely.
Negation	Negation is a special type of factuality. The truth value of statements is inverted: true statements become false, false statements become true.
Relation	Content-related link between exactly two annotates.
Sentence	A sequence of tokens that expresses a complete thought and consists of at least a subject and a predicate.
SCTID	In this guideline, the abbreviation <i>SCTID</i> is used to refer to the combination of SNOMED CT Concept ID and SNOMED CT FSN.
SNOMED CT Concept ID	The numeric identifier of a SNOMED CT concept.
SNOMED CT	An ontology-based terminology that contains a systematic description of clinical and medical procedures, substances, or other processes, including many synonyms in different languages, and relates them to each other.
SNOMED CT Fully Specified Name (FSN)	The SNOMED CT FSN is a unique description of the underlying clinical concept consisting of a descriptor and the SNOMED CT Semantic Tag.
SNOMED CT concept	A unit present in SNOMED CT that has concrete semantics. A concept can be assigned by annotating a text span. A SNOMED CT concept consists of a SNOMED CT Concept ID and a SNOMED CT FSN. SNOMED CT concepts are <i>precoordinated</i> if they are composed of several concepts.
SNOMED CT Semantic Tag	All SNOMED CT FSNs end with a <i>semantic tag</i> in parentheses after the descriptor. They indicate which content group a concept belongs to.
Text span	A sequence of tokens arranged consecutively in the text, but at least exactly one token.
Token	Smallest annotation-relevant unit. A token is a consecutive string of characters limited by spaces or other separators (e. g. “,”, “_”, “<”, “”, etc.).

Table 1: Definitions of important terms

2.1.1 Annotation Examples and Notation

Annotation examples are shown in this guideline as in (1): An annotated text span is embedded at least in sentence context and marked by square brackets as well as written in bold. After this text span, there is a letter indicating the exact SNOMED CT concept with which the text span was annotated. In addition, we show glossings for all examples, so non-German readers have a chance to understand the examples as well. The

Symbol	Meaning	Note
$\{x P(x)\}$	Set	The expression describes a set whose elements x all have the property $P(x)$.
$A \subseteq B$	A is a subset of B	Every element in A is also in B.
$A \subset B$	A is a strict subset of B	Every element in A is also in B, but A and B are not the same set.
$A \cap B$	The intersection of A and B	The set of elements that are in both A and B.
\emptyset	The empty set	The set with no elements.
$A \neq B$	A is not equal to B	The sets A and B are not identical.
$ A $	Cardinality of set A	The number of elements in A
$x \in A$	x is an element in A	x is an element, A is a set, and x is part of A
$x < y$	Inequality sign (less than)	x is less than y .
\forall	Universal quantifier	$\forall x \in A(P(x))$ means: "For all elements x in the set A, the property $P(x)$ holds."
\wedge	Logical AND	$P \wedge Q$ means that both P and Q are true.
\vee	Logical OR	$P \vee Q$ means that at least one of the two is true.
\neg	Logical NEGATION	$\neg P$ means that P is false.
\rightarrow	Logical CONDITIONAL	$P \rightarrow Q$ means that if P is true, Q is also true.
\Leftrightarrow	Logical BICONDITIONAL	$P \Leftrightarrow Q$ means that P is true exactly when Q is also true.
1 or 0	Truth values	1: A statement is true; 0: A statement is false.
$\llbracket P \rrbracket$	Denotation/interpretation	$\llbracket P \rrbracket$ is the meaning or interpretation of P.

Table 2: Definitions of formal symbols used in this guideline.

SNOMED CT concept is in turn shown below the sentence and consists of the SNOMED CT Concept ID and the SNOMED CT Fully Specified Name (FSN). The concrete example (2) illustrates that the concept designation "SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)" consists of the SNOMED CT Concept ID "386661006" and the SNOMED CT FSN "Fever (finding)".

- (1) Ich bin ein [Annotationsbeispiel](a.).
 - a. SCTID: SNOMED CT Concept ID | Deskriptor (SNOMED CT Semantic Tag)
Ich bin ein Annotationsbeispiel.
I am an annotation.example

‘I am an annotation example.’

- (2) Der Betroffene hat **[Fieber](a.)**.
- SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)
Der Betroffene hat Fieber.
the affected.person has fever
‘The affected person has fever.’

Relations between two concepts are represented by an arrow between the two concepts and labeled with the label $\vec{r}_{x,y}$. The first subscript letter denotes the source concept and the second the target concept of the relation. This is shown by way of example in (3).

- (3) Die **[Körpergröße](a.)** beträgt **[155](b.)** **[cm](c.)**.
- SCTID: 1153637007 | Body height (observable entity)
 - 155.0**
 - SCTID: 258672001 | Centimeter (qualifier value)
Die Körpergröße beträgt 155 cm.
the body.height amounts.to 155 cm
‘The body height is 155 cm.’

Note

Formal expressions are used in parts of this guideline. The logical formulas are not necessary for reading the guide, but merely serve to support understanding. An overview of the formal symbols used in this guideline can be found in Tab. 2.

2.2 Annotation Maxims

To mitigate the complexity of semantic concept annotation with SNOMED CT, six annotation maxims are introduced that must always be applied during the annotation process. The following annotation maxims are introduced:

1. Concept before Structure!
2. Better Together!
3. Identify the Meaning!
4. Stack with Care!
5. In doubt? Be broad!
6. Three Minutes Max!

Annotation Maxim I. Concept before Structure! The first maxim states that the text span to be annotated is always determined by the available SNOMED CT concepts. For example, the text spans “fell from the ladder”, “osteoarthritis in the right knee”, “diabetes mellitus type 1”, or “*Ascaris lumbricoides*” each correspond to a single SNOMED CT concept and not to a combination of different codes (see (4), (5), (6), and (7)). Thus, in most cases, a concept will span a larger number of tokens.

- (4) Bei Pt. ist [**Arthrose am rechten Knie**](a.) bekannt.
a. SCTID: 323321000119100 | Osteoarthritis of right knee joint (disorder)
Bei Pt. ist Arthrose am rechten Knie bekannt.
in patient is osteoarthritis at.the right knee known
‘Osteoarthritis of the right knee is known in the patient.’
- (5) Fr. Schubert ist [**von der Leiter gefallen**](a.).
a. SCTID: 86591008 | Fall from ladder (event)
Fr. Schubert ist von der Leiter gefallen.
Ms. Schubert is from the ladder fallen
‘Ms. Schubert fell from the ladder.’
- (6) [**Diabetes mellitus Typ 1**](a.) wird vermutet.
a. SCTID: 46635009 | Diabetes mellitus type 1 (disorder)
Diabetes mellitus Typ 1 wird vermutet.
diabetes mellitus type 1 is suspected
‘Diabetes mellitus type 1 is suspected.’
- (7) Wir gehen von einem [**Ascaris lumbricoides**](a.) aus.
a. SCTID: 19061001 | *Ascaris lumbricoides* (organism)
Wir gehen von einem *Ascaris lumbricoides* aus.
we go from an *Ascaris lumbricoides* out
‘We assume *Ascaris lumbricoides*.’

Annotation Maxim II. Better Together! Concept annotation can be tricky from time to time, since it is often unclear where the semantic and textual boundaries lie. The second maxim **Better Together!** provides clear rules for this:

Adjacent and meaningful: Every annotated text span should have a *meaning that is as specific as possible* and constitute a *meaningful, self-contained textual unit*. In this context, *adjacency* or *textual neighborhood*, i.e., the relative position of multiple tokens in the text, plays a substantial role. Linguistic units standing next to each other (**adjacency**) whose meaning can be represented with a SNOMED CT concept (**meaningfulness**) should be annotated jointly **where possible**. If two linguistic units are not contiguous, but separated by third concepts or sentence boundaries, they should not be annotated jointly, but individually. Ideally, the sentence *Patient comes with injured left hand* should therefore be annotated as in (8).

- (8) Patientin kommt mit [verletzter linker Hand](a.).
- a. SCTID: 11791321000119108 | Injury of left hand (disorder)
- Patientin kommt mit verletzter linker Hand.
patient.F comes with injured left hand
'The patient comes with an injured left hand.'

Pragmatics: meaningfulness before adjacency: All texts annotated within GeM-TeX undergo machine preannotation, i.e., the texts already contain SNOMED CT annotations. If the preannotation provides semantically correct but shorter-span concept annotations, these should be accepted. This also applies if a longer-span annotation would actually have been possible (e.g. due to adjacency). Accordingly, examples (9)-(11) would be equivalent to the reference solution (8).

- (9) Patientin kommt mit [verletzter](a.) [linker Hand](b.).
- a. SCTID: 417163006 | Traumatic or non-traumatic injury (disorder)
- b. SCTID: 85151006 | Structure of left hand (body structure)
- (10) Patientin kommt mit [verletzter](a.) [linker](b.) [Hand](c.).
- a. SCTID: 417163006 | Traumatic or non-traumatic injury (disorder)
- b. SCTID: 7771000 | Left (qualifier value)
- c. SCTID: 85562004 | Hand structure (body structure)
- (11) Patientin kommt mit [verletzer [linker](b.) Hand](a.).
- a. SCTID: 125599006 | Injury of hand (disorder)
- b. SCTID: 7771000 | Left (qualifier value)

In summary, Maxim II states that spans should be annotated as contiguously as possible if they are *adjacent* and *meaningful*. If this is not possible, shorter-span concepts may be used. The same applies if the preannotation suggests equivalent but shorter-span annotations: these are then to be accepted.

Annotation Maxim III. Identify the Meaning! Text spans should be annotated **exclusively** according to their actual meaning. The context **must** be taken into account

for every annotation. Anaphors must likewise be annotated with their intended meaning (see example (12)).

- (12) Die Rhythmusstörungen wurden mit [**Amiodaron**](a.) behandelt. Der Pat. hat [**das Medikament**](a.) wegen NW eigenmächtig abgesetzt.
- a. SCTID: 774551007 | Product containing only amiodarone (medicinal product)
- Die Rhythmusstörungen wurden mit Amiodaron behandelt. Der Pat.
the rhythm.disturbances were with amiodarone treated the patient
hat das Medikament wegen NW eigenmächtig abgesetzt.
has the medication because.of side.effects on.own.authority discontinued
‘The rhythm disturbances were treated with amiodarone. The patient discontinued the medication on his own initiative due to side effects.’

Ambiguities / multiple meanings should be resolved as far as possible according to the context or medical knowledge. If this is not possible, all plausible concepts should be assigned to this text span, resulting in so-called *stacked annotations*. (13) illustrates a lexical ambiguity: In German, the abbreviation *HWI* can equally stand for *urinary tract infection* or *posterior wall infarction*. If the ambiguity cannot be resolved through context, all **relevant**, possible concepts should be annotated as *stacked annotations*.

- (13) Wir stellen einen [[**HWI**](a.)](b.) fest.
- a. SCTID: 68566005 | Urinary tract infectious disease (disorder)
- b. SCTID: 233838001 | Acute posterior myocardial infarction (disorder)
- Wir stellen einen HWI fest.
we establish a HWI PRT
‘We diagnose an HWI.’

Note

As a general rule: Determiners (e.g. “the”, “a”) are not to be included in the annotation. Exceptions may be made if a determiner contributes meaning within the SNOMED CT concept, e.g. in the case of anaphors (see e.g. (12)), or as part of a prepositional phrase (see e.g. (24)). In Ex. (12), it becomes clear that the determiner “the” assumes a referential function (roughly: “It is THE, i.e. most recently mentioned, medication”)

Annotation Maxim IV. Stack with Care! Stacked annotations should generally be kept as minimal as possible. They are permitted only in the following situations:

- **Complete overlaps** are permitted for separated particle verbs and comparable insertions (see Maxim II).
- **Exact stacks** are permitted if text spans cannot be resolved unambiguously, if they are polysemous or ambiguous (see Maxim III).
- **Partial overlaps** are permitted if no complete SNOMED CT concept is suitable

for a longer span. Several SNOMED CT concepts can trigger an overlap.

Exceptions apply when, for example, equivalent preannotations are used (e.g. (11)).

Annotation Maxim V. In doubt? Be broad! The fifth annotation maxim is intended as pragmatic support for text passages that are difficult to annotate. In semantic annotation, the general rule is that text spans should be annotated with those concepts that are most exact for the given text passage (see Maxim III). However, if it is not clear during annotation whether, and if so which, more specific concept should be selected, the next higher *parent concept* should be used (see Section 3.1 for further explanations).

Annotation Maxim VI. Three Minutes Max! The sixth annotation maxim refers to the working time of the annotators. It becomes clear in the course of this document that semantic annotation with SNOMED CT can be a labor-intensive undertaking. To prevent annotators from getting lost in the greatest details of SNOMED CT, the research time should be regulated. The identification and annotation of a medical statement must not take longer than three minutes. The annotators should therefore first identify the main information of a medical statement. Subsequently, the SNOMED CT Browser should be consulted to find concept(s) for this main information, in order to then annotate them in INCEpTION. If important factualities are still present in the statement (e.g. negation), these should also be annotated (see Chapter 3.3.3.5). If, after the three minutes have elapsed, there is still further information in the respective text passage that is not main information, it is not annotated.

Note

It can be assumed that main information is mostly **Core concepts** (see Chapter 3.3.1).

This procedure will be illustrated once using example (14). First, the core statements of the sentence must be identified: (i) There is hypertrophy of the left ventricle and (ii) the function is not impaired. For statement (i), we should therefore find a concept that expresses hypertrophy of the left ventricle, as shown in (15). Likewise, we search for a Core concept that describes the function as in (16). Next, further concepts are searched for that modify the Core concepts in the text (see (17) & (18)). Two alternatives can be chosen for embedding the span “concentric”: In (19), the span “concentrically hypertrophied” is annotated with the SNOMED CT concept “SCTID: 34344004 | Concentric hypertrophy (morphologic abnormality)” overlapping with the span “hypertrophied left ventricle”. In (20), by contrast, the short span “concentric” is annotated with the concept “SCTID: 255465008 | Concentric (qualifier value)”.

- (14) Normalgroßer konzentrisch hypertropher linker Ventrikel mit noch guter normal-sized concentrically hypertrophied left ventricle with still good LV-Funktion.
LV-function
‘Normal-sized, concentrically hypertrophied left ventricle with still good LV function.’

- (15) Normalgroßer konzentrisch [**hypertropher linker Ventrikel**](a.) mit noch guter LV-Funktion.
- SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
- (16) Normalgroßer konzentrisch [**hypertropher linker Ventrikel**](a.) mit noch guter [**LV-Funktion**](b.).
- SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
 - SCTID: 366188009 | Finding of left ventricular function (finding)
- (17) Normalgroßer konzentrisch [**hypertropher linker Ventrikel**](a.) mit noch [**guter**](b.) [**LV-Funktion**](c.).
- SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
 - SCTID: 20572008 | Good (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 366188009 | Finding of left ventricular function (finding)
- (18) [**Normalgroßer**](a.) konzentrisch [**hypertropher linker Ventrikel**](b.) mit noch [**guter**](c.) [**LV-Funktion**](d.).
- SCTID: 53461003 | Normal size (finding)
 - SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
 - SCTID: 20572008 | Good (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 366188009 | Finding of left ventricular function (finding)
- (19) [**Normalgroßer**](a.) [**konzentrisch** [**hypertropher**](b.) **linker Ventrikel**](c.) mit noch [**guter**](d.) [**LV-Funktion**](e.).
- SCTID: 53461003 | Normal size (finding)
 - SCTID: 34344004 | Concentric hypertrophy (morphologic abnormality)
 - SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
 - SCTID: 20572008 | Good (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 366188009 | Finding of left ventricular function (finding)
- (20) [**Normalgroßer**](a.) [**konzentrisch**](b.) [**hypertropher linker Ventrikel**](c.) mit noch [**guter**](d.) [**LV-Funktion**](e.).
- SCTID: 53461003 | Normal size (finding)
 - SCTID: 255465008 | Concentric (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 55827005 | Left ventricular hypertrophy (disorder)
 - SCTID: 20572008 | Good (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 366188009 | Finding of left ventricular function (finding)

2.3 Linguistic Phenomena

1. **(Syntactic) coordination** is present when two or more linguistic units are positioned separately, e.g. by a conjunction or an enumeration, but fulfill the same syntactic function. Coordinated units are spatially separated by separators or junctions, **are considered non-adjacent and should therefore generally be annotated separately from one another**.

In Ex. (21), it can be seen that the last coordinated unit (“ears”) and the coordination predicate (“third-degree burned”) should be annotated separately despite adjacency. The

background for this instruction is the equal treatment of all coordinated units. In the relation annotation introduced later, it is noted that coordinated units should be connected to their respective coordination predicate by means of a relation in order to do justice to their meaning.

(21) [Kopf](a.) und [Ohren](b.) [drittgradig verbrannt](c.).

a. SCTID: 69536005 | Head structure (body structure)

b. SCTID: 117590005 | Ear structure (body structure)

c. SCTID: 1403192003 | Full thickness burn (disorder)

Kopf und Ohren drittgradig verbrannt.

head and ears third.degree burned

‘Head and ears third-degree burned.’

Coordinated units and their coordination predicate should, in such cases, exceptionally be annotated as one span if there is a SNOMED CT concept that precisely describes the text span, as for example in (22).

- (22) Es gibt eine [Verbrennung 3. Grades am Kopf und Nacken](a.).
- a. SCTID: 741070003 | Full thickness burn of head and neck (disorder)
- Es gibt eine Verbrennung 3. Grades am Kopf und Nacken.
 it gives a burn third degree at.the head and neck
 ‘There is a third-degree burn of the head and neck.’

2. Copulas are words or phrases that syntactically connect two sentence constituents but have no semantic meaning of their own. A typical example is inflected forms of the verb “to be”. **Due to the lack of semantic contribution, expressions separated by copulas are considered adjacent and should be annotated jointly.** In (23), one can see that, with the exception of the determiner “the”, the entire sentence should be assigned to the concept “SCTID: 287139006 | Epidermal burn of head (disorder)”.

- (23) Der [Kopf ist erstgradig verbrannt](a.).
- a. SCTID: 287139006 | Epidermal burn of head (disorder)
- Der Kopf ist erstgradig verbrannt.
 the head is first.degree burned
 ‘The head is first-degree burned.’

3. Particle verbs and other insertions. Particle verbs are verbs that contain a particle, e.g. a preposition (e.g. “give up”). In many cases, the particle can be separated from the main verb in special syntactic formations. Separated particle verbs and their insertions should be annotated overlappingly. However, it is important that the insertions are spatially *completely* contained in the outer annotation. An example can be found in (24), where the insertion (“after the surgery”) is completely contained in the matrix annotation (“stopped [...] smoking”).

- (24) Er [hörte [nach der OP](b.) mit dem Rauchen auf](a.).
- a. SCTID: 160617001 | Stopped smoking (finding)
- b. SCTID: 262061000 | Postoperative period (qualifier value)
- Er hörte nach der OP mit dem Rauchen auf.
 he stopped after the surgery with the smoking PRT
 ‘He stopped smoking after the surgery.’

3 Concept Annotation

The annotation of text spans based on SNOMED CT concepts is the basis of semantic annotation in GeMTeX. The rest of the chapter is devoted to the formal description of concept annotation (Chap. 3.1), a short section on the SNOMED CT Semantic Tags (Chap. 3.2), and the detailed description of relevant SNOMED CT concepts (Chap. 3.3). Section 3.4 is devoted to handling clinical manifestations in family members.

3.1 Semantics of concept annotation

The annotation of text spans follows a simple rule: A text span that is as specific as possible must be assigned a meaning that is as unambiguous and meaningful as possible. **Meaning** is defined as a concept present in SNOMED CT. **Unambiguity** means that a text span TS is assigned only one concept c within the semantic domain D_e , provided that the text span does not exhibit ambiguities (cf. Maxim III). The **semantic domain** D_e defines the concepts permitted for annotation and denotes (=means or includes), in our case, the set of all concepts C that belong to a concept group in SNOMED CT that is discussed in this guideline (see (25)).

- (25) a. $C \subseteq \text{SNOMED CT} - \{\text{attributes, meta data, situations with explicit context}\}$
b. $D_e = \{c \mid c \in C\}$

A **text span** TS corresponds to the non-empty set of sequential tokens t from the set of all tokens T of a document (see (26)). The smallest linguistic unit to be annotated is always a token - tokens must not be “broken up”. Exceptions to this rule include, for example, incorrectly concatenated expressions (e.g. “li<re”) or numerical values and their units. If such spans are written together (“3cm”), they may be split into their individual tokens, i.e. numerical value and unit (“3” and “cm”).

- (26) a. $T = \{t_k \mid k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}\}$
b. $TS = \{t_k \mid k \in I\}$ where:
 $I = \{s, s + 1, \dots, n\} \wedge 1 \leq s \leq n$

The concepts in SNOMED CT are organized *hierarchically*. Very general concepts branch into increasingly specific concepts. Every concept that has more specific concepts below it belongs to the set of parent concepts C_P .

Every concept that has no further subordinate concepts belongs to the set of terminal concepts C_T . Both sets are subsets of all concepts C and are mutually exclusive (see (27)).

- (27) a. $\{C_P, C_T\} \subseteq C$
b. $C_P \cap C_T = \emptyset$

The annotations should be as specific as possible, i.e. more specific parent concepts are generally to be preferred over more general parent concepts, and terminal concepts over parent concepts, provided that the context allows it and nothing is interpreted “into the text span”.

Using Fig. 1, the hierarchical structure of SNOMED CT (a directed acyclic graph, i.e. a polyhierarchy) is briefly illustrated.

Figure 1: Hierarchical Structure of SNOMED CT

The parent concept “SCTID: 404684003 | Clinical Finding” has a more specific child concept “SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)”. The latter is in turn a parent concept, e.g. for the even more specific concept “SCTID: 9619006 | Aseptic fever (finding)”. Since the latter has no further children, it is a terminal concept. It also becomes clear that a SNOMED CT concept can have multiple parent concepts: “SCTID: 240822009 | Bancroftian filarial fever” is a child of both “SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)” and “SCTID: 240821002 | Early bancroftian filariasis”.

Based on Fig. 1, the relationships between the concepts shown in (28) can be inferred: *Clinical Finding* and *Fever* belong to the parent concepts C_P , while *Aseptic Fever* and *Bancroftian filarial fever* belong to the set of terminal concepts C_T . At the same time, *Fever* and *Fever due to infection*, *Aseptic fever* and *Bancroftian filarial fever* are child concepts of *Clinical Finding*. As already shown, *Bancroftian filarial fever* is a child of two concepts: *Fever* and *Early bancroftian filariasis*.

The semantics of an annotated text span $[TS](C^*)$ is defined as follows: First, a text span must be annotated with at least one concept (see (29)). Furthermore, an annotation is *applicable* or *correct* exactly if the selected concept c is part of the semantic domain D_e , is semantically compatible with the marked text span TS , and there is no alternative concept c' in D_e that is likewise compatible with TS and more detailed than c (see (30)). Semantic compatibility between a text span and a concept is present if TS is an instance

of c , is equivalent to c , or represents a subclass of c (see (31)). In all other cases, the annotation is *not applicable* or *incorrect* and therefore should not be selected.

- (28) a. {Fever, Clinical Finding, Early bancroftian filariasis} $\subset C_P$
 b. {Aseptic Fever, Bancroftian filarial fever} $\subset C_T$
 c. {Fever, Fever due to infection, Aseptic Fever, Bancroftian filarial fever} \subset Clinical Finding
 d. Bancroftian filarial fever \in {Fever, Early bancroftian filariasis}

$$(29) \quad \llbracket [TS](C^*) \rrbracket = \begin{cases} 1 : & C^* \neq \emptyset \\ 0 : & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$(30) \quad C^* = \{c \in D_e \wedge \text{compatible}(TS, c) \wedge \forall c' \in C(\text{compatible}(TS, c') \rightarrow \text{detail}(c') \leq \text{detail}(c))\}$$

$$(31) \quad \llbracket \text{compatible}(TS, c) \rrbracket = \begin{cases} 1 : & \text{instance}(TS, c) \vee \text{equivalence}(TS, c) \vee \text{subclass}(TS, c) \\ 0 : & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

a. $\llbracket \text{instance}(TS, c) \rrbracket = TS \in \{x \mid x = \text{specific, individual occurrence of } c\}$
 b. $\llbracket \text{equivalence}(TS, c) \rrbracket = TS \in \{x \mid x \text{ is synonymous with } c\}$
 c. $\llbracket \text{subclass}(TS, c) \rrbracket = TS \in \{x \mid x \subset c\}$

Note

The condition in (31-c) allows a text span to be assigned a parent concept of the (presumably) actually correct concept. Such an annotation is therefore considered correct, although it is somewhat imprecise. It is advisable to discuss such spans with the local annotation lead.

If the text span “fever” in example (32) were annotated with the concept “SCTID: 9619006 | Aseptic fever”, the annotation would be incorrect. This concept is indeed part of the semantic domain and also more detailed than the concept “SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)”. However, it is not compatible with the text span, since no information exists as to whether the affected person has aseptic fever or not. Formally, none of the compatibility conditions introduced in (31) applies either: The text span “fever” is not an instance of “SCTID: 9619006 | Aseptic fever”, since “fever” is not a specific or individual occurrence of the concept, but a very general description of a medical condition. Text span and concept are not equivalent, since they are not synonymous. Finally, it can also be stated that “fever” is not a subclass or subset of the concept “SCTID: 9619006 | Aseptic fever” either; in fact, the opposite is true.⁸ The example also illustrates that more specific concepts should only be selected if they are also expressed by the text (cf. Maxim III).

⁸The example also illustrates that the reverse case would be less problematic. If the SNOMED CT concept “SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)” were assigned to the text span “aseptic fever”, it would not be specific enough. However, it would satisfy the compatibility condition in (31) due to the definition (31-c). Because: The text span “aseptic fever” is a subclass of the concept “SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)”.

- (32) Der Betroffene hat **[Fieber](a.)**.
- a. SCTID: 386661006 | Fever (finding)
- Der Betroffene hat Fieber.
the affected.person has fever
'The affected person has fever.'

Since the number of specific parent or terminal concepts in SNOMED CT is immense, the rest of the chapter explains a selection of general parent concepts or Semantic Tags, and more specific parent concepts and terminal concepts are listed by way of example. While the concepts listed in the guidelines are not exhaustive, the concept groups that are introduced serve as a guideline for annotation. Formally, they and their child concepts denote the semantic domain D_e of the GeMTeX annotation (cf. (25)).

3.2 SNOMED CT Semantic Tags

An elementary building block for determining whether a SNOMED CT concept fits the marked span (i.e. is *compatible*) are the SNOMED CT Semantic Tags. They are always found in parentheses in the SNOMED CT FSN and indicate to which concept group a particular SNOMED CT concept belongs. In general, one can usually follow one’s intuition here: If, for example, the text discusses an existing disease or a diagnosis, the concept should usually have the Semantic Tag “(finding)” or “(disorder)”. The tags “(body structure)” or “(qualifier)” would be rather inappropriate here.

Figure 2: The concept “SCTID: 125666000 | Burn (disorder)” in the SNOMED CT International SNOMED CT Browser.

Example (33) illustrates that Semantic Tags are elementary for finding the correct concept: There are two very similar-sounding concepts for burn in SNOMED CT: “SCTID: 125666000 | Burn (disorder)” and “SCTID: 48333001 | Burn injury (morphologic abnormality)”. The Semantic Tag “(disorder)” shows that concept (a.) belongs to the group of *Disorders* (in German, the paraphrases *abnormal clinical conditions / diseases / disorders* come very close). As described in more detail in the following Chapter 3.3, this group of concepts belongs to the *Core concepts*, which should be used especially when clinical pictures or diagnoses are described. The second concept belongs to the group “(morphologic abnormality)”, which can usually be used to describe, for example, tissue changes as a consequence of a burn (e.g. in radiology or pathology reports). Depending on the letter context, the Semantic Tag can therefore help identify the correct concept.

- (33) Der Patient leidet unter einer [[**Verbrennung**](a.)](b.).
- SCTID: 125666000 | Burn (disorder)
 - SCTID: 48333001 | Burn injury (morphologic abnormality)
- Der Patient leidet unter einer Verbrennung.
the patient suffers under a burn
‘The patient suffers from a burn.’

Note

Of course, the SNOMED CT Semantic Tags are not sufficient to determine whether a concept is the correct one or not. The SNOMED CT International SNOMED CT Browser provides further help: If one looks at the entry for the concept “SCTID: 125666000 | Burn (disorder)”, the concept “SCTID: 48333001 | Burn injury (morphologic abnormality)” is shown as an axiom for the associated morphology (see Fig. 2). From this it can be concluded that the latter concept should really only be used in cases where the morphological change is actually being referred to.

3.2.1 Excluded Semantic Tags:

The following hierarchies are excluded from GeMTeX annotation:

- Environment/Geographical Location
- Subhierarchies of qualifiers:
 - Action
 - Overlapping sites
- Record artifact
- Situation with explicit context
- SNOMED CT Model Component
- Social context (except: *person*)
- Special concept
- Staging and scales

This corresponds to the following list of Semantic Tags:

(action)	(assessment scale)
(attribute)	(core metadata concept)
(environment)	(ethnic group)
(foundation metadata concept)	(geographic location)
(life style)	(link assertion)
(linkage concept)	(namespace concept)
(navigational concept)	(occupation)(inactive concept)
(owl metadata concept)	(overlapping sites)
(racial group)	(record artifact)
(religion/philosophy)	(situation)
(social concept)	(staging scale)
(tumor staging)	

Table 3: Excluded Semantic Tags

The hierarchies *Physical Force* are to be used only in exceptional cases.

3.3 Concepts in SNOMED CT

This section introduces the three concept types relevant for semantic annotation in GeM-TeX: **Core concepts** (Chap. 3.3.1), **Modifier concepts** (Chap. 3.3.2), and **Qualifier concepts** (Chap. 3.3.3). Core concepts are considered the most relevant concept group, and their entities should be annotated as completely as possible. Modifier concepts are somewhat less relevant, but nevertheless encode important medical information. Qualifier concepts carry the least relevance, but are often very well suited to specify Core or Modifier concepts. All annotation examples in this section are *not complete*, but each focuses on the concept that is to be illustrated. Fully annotated sentence examples can be found in Chap. 6.

3.3.1 Core concepts

Core concepts comprise the largest and clinically most relevant concepts and are divided into the following four categories: **Condition**, **Procedure**, **Medications & Substances**, and **Observables**. Core concepts are usually fully defined, thus already contain many sufficient and necessary conditions, and are therefore the basic building block for semantic annotation.

3.3.1.1 Condition

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Condition**| stands for health-related phenomena, events, processes, or states in the broadest sense. In SNOMED CT, these are the contents of the hierarchies under “SCTID: 404684003 | Clinical finding (finding)”, “SCTID: 64572001 | Disease (disorder)”, and “SCTID: 272379006 | Event (event)”. Excluded, however, are those that are intentionally caused by healthcare professionals (see Procedures).

|**Clinical finding**| represents the result of a clinical observation, assessment, or evaluation. It contains normal and abnormal clinical states (e.g. |asthma|, |headache|, |normal breath sounds|). The hierarchy under |clinical finding| contains concepts that are to be used for diagnoses.

|**Disorders**| are permanent or temporary abnormal clinical states with an underlying pathological process that may be under treatment.

|**Events**| are occurrences that affect health or care, but - as already mentioned at the beginning - are not procedures or interventions.

Usable Semantic Tags: (*finding*), (*disorder*), (*event*)

Condition comprises *Clinical Findings*, *Disorders*, and *Events*. Thus, *Condition* includes everything that characterizes a patient in their organism or living environment. This includes diseases, symptoms, findings, or phenotypes. In everyday terms, Condition therefore includes *everything that someone has or that happens to someone*, with the exception of Procedures (see 3.3.1.2). One example each of a Clinical Finding, Disorder, and Event can be found in examples (34), (35), and (36).

- (34) Sympomatik: [**Anarthrie**](a.).
- a. SCTID: 48257004 | Anarthria (finding)
 Sympomatik Anarthrie.
 symptoms anarthria
 ‘Symptoms: anarthria.’
- (35) Pat. leidet unter [**spastischer Paraplegie Typ 2**] (a.).
- a. SCTID: 723622007 | X-linked spastic paraplegia type 2 (disorder)
 Pat. leidet unter spastischer Paraplegie Typ 2.
 patient suffers under spastic paraplegia type 2
 ‘The patient suffers from spastic paraplegia type 2.’
- (36) Betroffene wurde [**von Hund gebissen**](a.).
- a. SCTID: 217697000 | Dog bite (event)
 Betroffene wurde von Hund gebissen.
 affected.person was by dog bitten
 ‘The affected person was bitten by a dog.’

3.3.1.2 Procedure

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Procedure**| represents measures or procedures of healthcare. This includes not only invasive procedures, but also the administration of medicinal products, imaging procedures, training, therapies, and administrative procedures (e.g. |appendectomy|, |physiotherapy|, |subcutaneous injection|). In SNOMED CT, procedures can be found under “SCTID: 71388002 | Procedure (procedure)”

Usable Semantic Tags: (*procedure*), (*regime/therapy*)

Procedures are all examinations and measures that happen to a patient (see (37)).

- (37) Nach erfolgreicher [**Blutabnahme**](a.) wurde die [**Implantation**](b.) durchgeführt.
- a. SCTID: 82078001 | Collection of blood specimen for laboratory (procedure)
 - b. SCTID: 782902008 | Implantation procedure (procedure)
 Nach erfolgreicher Blutabnahme wurde die Implantation durchgeführt.
 after successful blood.collection was the implantation performed
 ‘After successful blood collection, the implantation was performed.’

3.3.1.3 Pharmaceutical/Biological Product & Substance

Medications and other substances are annotated as Pharmaceutical/Biological Product or Substance. An element of the category Pharmaceutical/Biological Product can be informally defined as *everything that has a package leaflet*. Pharmaceutical products should generally be annotated based on their active substances with the SNOMED CT Semantic Tag “(medicinal product)”. These concepts can be found under “SCTID: 763158003 |

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Pharmaceutical/biological product**| represents pharmaceutical products (e.g. |amoxicillin 250mg capsule|, |paracetamol + codeine tablet|)

|**Substance**| represents general substances, the chemical constituents of pharmaceutical and biological products, body substances, food constituents, and diagnostics (e.g. |methane|, |insulin|, |albumin|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*product*), (*medicinal product*), (*clinical drug*), (*medicinal product form*), (*substance*)

Medicinal product (product)” and are always structured according to the pattern “Product containing *X*, *Y*, ...”. In some cases, the decision is very simple, see Ex. (38).

- (38) Die Pt.in nahm selbstständig [**Aspirin**](a.) ein.
a. SCTID: 774656009 | Product containing only aspirin (medicinal product)
Die Pt.in nahm selbstständig Aspirin ein.
the patient.F took independently aspirin PRT
‘The patient independently took aspirin.’

In other situations, annotation can be more difficult. The product names *Voltaren* or *Vokanamet* are not contained in SNOMED CT. Such spans should also be annotated with a concept that carries the Semantic Tag “(medicinal product)”. Since *Voltaren* consists of the active substance *diclofenac* and *Vokanamet* consists of *canagliflozin* and *metformin*, the spans are annotated sufficiently precisely with the concepts shown in (39) and (40).

- (39) Der Patientin wird [**Voltaren**](a.) verschrieben.
a. SCTID: 3775563008 | Product containing only diclofenac (medicinal product)
Der Patientin wird Voltaren verschrieben.
the patient.F.DAT is Voltaren prescribed
‘The patient is prescribed Voltaren.’
- (40) Wir verschreiben [**Vokanamet**](a.).
a. SCTID: 775026006 | Product containing only canagliflozin and metformin (medicinal product)
Wir verschreiben Vokanamet.
we prescribe Vokanamet
‘We prescribe Vokanamet.’

Note

If a product consists of several active substances and there is no suitable pre-coordinated concept in SNOMED CT, the two active substances are stacked. It must be ensured that the stacked concepts **do not** carry the word *only* in the descriptor.

The annotation of text spans with a concept with the Semantic Tag “(substance)” should only be performed if a text span in the letter context is to be understood explicitly not as a product, but as a substance (cf. (41)).

- (41) Die Analyse zeigte, dass [Methylprednisolon](a.) im Blut der Pt. war.
a. SCTID: 116593003 | Methylprednisolone (substance)
Die Analyse zeigte dass Methylprednisolon im Blut der Pt. war.
the analysis showed that methylprednisolone in.the blood the patient was
‘The analysis showed that methylprednisolone was in the patient’s blood.’

Information on quantities, dosage forms, or administration forms should **not be annotated by the annotators**, but only by the machine preannotation. These letter areas should be marked with the `No_Human` layer in INCEPTION (see Section 4).

3.3.1.4 Observables

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Observable entity**| represents a question or examination that can lead to an answer or result, (e.g. |systolic blood pressure|, |color of iris|, |gender|)

|**Staging and scales**| represents assessment schemes and tumor staging systems (e.g. |Glasgow ComaScale|, |FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*observable entity*), (*tumor staging*), (*finding*)

Observables include all examinations or queryable and observable parameters that result in a defined result or measured values and often also have a unit. Staging and Scales describes and comprises the assessment of disease stages and severity or risk grades, and thus also various test scales (*assessment scales*). Text spans that contain scores should generally be annotated as *observable entities* and not as *assessment scale*, since many scales map to more than one test score.

An example is the *Aachen Aphasia Test*: The concept “SCTID: 273251005 | Aachen aphasia test (assessment scale)” is a scale that contains the scale parameter “SCTID: 714474007 | Aachen Aphasia Test score (observable entity)”. Only the latter is used for annotation, since it is more precise (cf. also (42)).

- (42) Das [**Geschlecht**](a.), die [**Sauerstoffkonzentration**](b.) und die Ergebnisse des [**Glasgow Coma Score**](c.) des Patienten werden nachstehend aufgelistet.
- SCTID: 263495000 | Gender (observable entity)
 - SCTID: 250772006 | Oxygen concentration (observable entity)
 - SCTID: 248241002 | Glasgow coma score (observable entity)

Das Geschlecht die Sauerstoffkonzentration und die Ergebnisse des
the gender the oxygen.concentration and the results of.the
Glasgow Coma Score des Patienten werden nachstehend aufgelistet.
Glasgow Coma Score of.the patient are below listed

‘The patient’s gender, oxygen concentration, and Glasgow Coma Score re-
sults are listed below.’

It should also be noted that many Observable concepts have Finding concepts with the same name, e.g. for “SCTID: 75367002 | Blood pressure (observable entity)” the concept “SCTID: 392570002 | Blood pressure finding (finding)”. Finding concepts should only be given priority over Observable Entity concepts if they represent the situation described in the text more accurately. This can be the case, for example, if the Finding concept is a combination of an Observable Entity concept and a Qualifier concept (e.g. “SCTID: 81010002 | Decreased systolic arterial pressure (finding)”). A rule of thumb is: If the measurement of a specific value is foregrounded, choose the Observable; if the measurement result is *interpreted*, choose the Finding.

In general: For all annotations with an Observable concept, there is usually a qualitative or quantitative value in the text, in the latter case usually also a unit (cf. (43)). For many observations, there are no Observable concepts, especially in laboratory examinations. Here, SNOMED CT requires suitable Procedure concepts (under “SCTID: 386053000 |

Evaluation procedure (procedure)”) to be used instead. For example: In the text span “leukocytes 8000 / µl” (as part of the blood count), “leukocytes” is annotated with “SCTID: 767002 | White blood cell count (procedure)”. In the span “glucose in urine 15 mg/dl”, “glucose in urine” is annotated with “SCTID: 30994003 | Glucose measurement, urine (procedure)”.

(43) Der [**Blutzuckerwert**](a.) des Patienten betrug [**135**](b.) [**mg/dl**](c.) bei der morgendlichen Messung

a. SCTID: 434912009 | Blood glucose concentration (observable entity)

b. **135.0**

c. SCTID: 258797006 | Milligram/deciliter (qualifier value)

Der Blutzuckerwert des Patienten betrug 135 mg/dl bei der
the blood.glucose.value of.the patient amounted.to 135 mg/dl at the
morgendlichen Messung.

morning measurement

‘The patient’s blood glucose value was 135 mg/dl in the morning measurement.’

3.3.2 Modifier concepts

Modifiers describe core concepts in more detail and thereby answer, for example, which anatomical structure is involved, which devices are used, or which organisms are involved in a disease, but also substances and external factors such as electrical voltage or radiation. The following Modifier concepts are defined for annotation: **Body Structures**, **Physical Objects**, and **Organisms**.

3.3.2.1 Body Structure

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Body structure**| represents normal and abnormal anatomical structures (e.g. |mitral valve structure|, |adenosarcoma|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*body structure*), (*morphologic abnormality*)

Body Structures are all parts of the body, from large structures such as the head or organs such as the brain, down to tissue. As described in the basic rules for annotation, the annotation should be exactly as specific as the text allows (see (44)). Body parts should always be annotated as *Body Structure*, and in the case of pathological findings possibly as *Specimen*. Most anatomical structures are found twice in SNOMED CT, e.g. “SCTID: 56459004 | Foot structure (body structure)” and “SCTID: 302545001 | Entire foot (body structure)”. The former refers to the named structures, but also to any parts of them. In general, for localization information, the former type of concepts (with “*structure*” in the descriptor) should be preferred. Concepts containing “*entire*” should only be used if an entire body structure is actually being captured. This can be important, for example, in amputations. Thus, an amputation *at* the foot probably means an amputation of any part of the entire foot structure (i.e.: “SCTID: 56459004 | Foot structure (body structure)”). The amputation *of* the foot, however, describes the amputation of the entire foot (i.e.: “SCTID: 302545001 | Entire foot (body structure)”). In most cases, however, annotation of anatomical structures is unnecessary because these are contained in Core concepts (e.g.: “SCTID: 723312009 | Amputation of right foot (procedure)”).

- (44) Wir untersuchten [**Kopf**](a.) und [**Haut**](b.).
- SCTID: 69536005 | Head structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 39937001 | Skin structure (body structure)
- Wir untersuchten Kopf und Haut.
we examined head and skin
‘We examined the head and skin.’

3.3.2.2 Physical Object

Devices and other objects that can be transplanted, inserted, or otherwise used in diagnostics and therapy fall under the parent concept **Physical Object** (see (45-a)). In certain cases, attention must be paid to the wording: In (45-c), the pacemaker is actually in the patient and should therefore be interpreted as a Finding. In (46), it is only a recommendation regarding the device and should therefore be annotated as *Physical*

SNOMED CT Definition

|Physical object| represents natural and human-made material objects(e.g. |vena cava filter|, |implant device|, |automobile|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*physical object*)

Object. The same applies to the coil: The coil in example (45) is present in the patient and would therefore have to be interpreted as a Finding. However, there is no such concept in SNOMED CT. Therefore, the SNOMED CT axioms of related terms should be used. Fig. 3 shows that concept (45-c) has, among other things, the axiom “**has interpretation** → **Present**”. Clicking on this axiom leads to the qualifier concept “SCTID: 52101004 | Present (qualifier value)”. This concept should therefore be stacked over the text span as a specifying annotation (see Annotation Maxim IV; more on qualifier concepts can be found in Section 3.3.3).⁹

- (45) Die Patientin besitzt **[[Spirale](a.)](b.)** und **[Herzschrittmacher](c.)**.
- a. SCTID: 312082008 | Contraceptive coil (physical object)
 - b. SCTID: 52101004 | Present (qualifier value)
 - c. SCTID: 441509002 | Cardiac pacemaker in situ (finding)
- Die Patientin besitzt Spirale und Herzschrittmacher.
the patient.F possesses coil and pacemaker
‘The patient has a coil and a pacemaker.’
- (46) Dem Patienten wird zu einem **[Herzschrittmacher](a.)** geraten.
- a. SCTID: 424921004 | Permanent cardiac pacemaker, device (physical object)
- Dem Patienten wird zu einem Herzschrittmacher geraten.
the patient.DAT is to a pacemaker advised
‘The patient is advised to get a pacemaker.’

Figure 3: Screenshot of SNOMED CT axioms.

⁹It becomes clear that Physical Objects that are actually present in the body should generally also be additionally annotated with the concept “SCTID: 52101004 | Present (qualifier value)” mentioned here, provided that there is no precoordinated concept.

3.3.2.3 Organisms

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Organism**| represents organisms that are relevant in human or veterinary medicine.
(e.g. |streptococcus pyogenes|, |beagle|, |texon cattle breed|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*organism*)

Organisms describe all types of organisms such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites (see (47)). In addition, as in (48), larger organisms can also occur. The rule is: If more specific information is present in the text, such as *subtypes* or *genetic strains* of the organisms, these concepts are to be preferred over the general ones.

(47) [**Staphylococcus aureus**](**a.**) wurde nicht festgestellt.

a. SCTID: 3092008 | Staphylococcus aureus (organism)

Staphylococcus aureus wurde nicht festgestellt.

Staphylococcus aureus was not detected

‘Staphylococcus aureus was not detected.’

(48) Vater von Pt. besitzt [**Hund**](**a.**). Pt. gibt an gebissen worden zu sein.

a. SCTID: 448771007 | Dog

Vater von Pt. besitzt Hund. Pt. gibt an gebissen worden zu sein.
father of patient owns dog patient states PRT bitten been to

be

‘The patient’s father owns a dog. The patient states that they were bitten.’

3.3.3 Qualifier concepts

SNOMED CT Definition

|**Qualifier value**| represents values of some attributes of SNOMED CT, insofar as these values are not subtypes of other top-level concepts. (e.g. |left|, |abnormal result|, |severe|)

Usable Semantic Tags: (*qualifier value*), (*date*)

Qualifiers are a very general group of concepts in SNOMED CT. Among other things, *numbers*, *units*, *time specifications*, and *negation* fall into this category. Under |**Qualifier value**| there are also concepts that one might consider using alone for the annotation of diagnoses or procedures, such as “SCTID: 260976002 | Presence of infection (qualifier value)” or “SCTID: 1055212009 | Losing weight process (qualifier value)”. **Conditions or Procedures are always to be preferred over these concepts**; the latter should only be used if there are no suitable concepts under the Core Concepts.

With Qualifiers, there is often an agony of choice, since concepts are very similar and no definitions are available. Here, one should always give preference to the concepts that are used in similar contexts in SNOMED CT axioms.

As an example, the attribute “high” is considered in more detail. In the span “high risk of stroke”, “high” could be annotated with “SCTID: 75540009 | High (qualifier value)”, “SCTID: 35105006 | Increased (qualifier value)”, or “SCTID: 281302008 | Above reference range (qualifier value)”. The search for similar precoordinated concepts in SNOMED CT will end at the concept “SCTID: 161640005 | At high risk for heart disease (finding)”. This is by definition linked to “SCTID: 75540009 | High (qualifier value)”, so the latter would also be used for “high” in “high risk of stroke”. However, if one takes the span “high aluminum concentration in blood”, analysis of the similar but precoordinated concept “SCTID: 166689004 | Serum potassium level above reference range (finding)” shows the use of “SCTID: 281302008 | Above reference range (qualifier value)”. This suggests interpreting the word “high” in the span “high aluminum concentration in blood” with the concept “SCTID: 281302008 | Above reference range (qualifier value)”.

Note

The general rule is: We assume that concepts do not have special characteristics. An exception is the explicit mention that something about the measured value or finding is special. If something in a clinical text is explicitly described as “too high”, this must be marked accordingly: The span “too high” is annotated with the suitable concept (see above). The same also applies if something is explicitly labeled as “unremarkable” or “normal”: This word is to be annotated with the SNOMED CT concept “SCTID: 17621005 | Normal (qualifier value)”.

3.3.3.1 Time specifications

All **time and date specifications**, e.g. *admission* and *discharge dates*, *dates of birth*, or specifications that refer to *previous diagnoses or procedures*, should be annotated (see (49)). All absolute time specifications should be annotated as “SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value)” and then normalized. For this, the marked date is entered in INCEpTION in the `literal` field in the form `yyyy-mm-dd`. If parts of the date are not known, the affected positions are replaced by the letter ‘x’ (see (49-b)). For relative date specifications, only the temporal units (e.g. “day” or “week”) are to be annotated. (see (50)). Normalization is not intended here.

(49) Fr. Maier (geb. [10. März 1965](a.)) wurde im [Dezember 2021](b.) entlassen.

a. SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value) (1965-03-10)

b. SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value) (2021-12-xx)

Fr. Maier geboren 10. März 1965 wurde im Dezember 2021

Ms. Maier born 10 March 1965 was in.the December 2021

entlassen.

discharged

‘Ms. Maier, born March 10, 1965, was discharged in December 2021.’

(50) Laut Patient bestehen die Sehstörungen seit [drei](a.) [Wochen](b.) und [6](c.) [Tagen](d.).

a. (3.0)

b. SCTID: 258705008 | week (qualifier value)

c. (6.0)

d. SCTID: 258703001 | day (qualifier value)

Laut Patient bestehen die Sehstörungen seit drei Wochen

according.to patient exist the visual.disturbances since three weeks

und 6 Tagen.

and 6 days

‘According to the patient, the visual disturbances have existed for three weeks and six days.’

If an entity stands in a temporal relation to another entity, this must be expressed by child concepts of “SCTID: 272112001 | Relative times (qualifier value)”. As shown in Tab. 4, only those temporal relations should be annotated that are also explicitly expressed (i.e., we annotate posteriority only if we find a corresponding linguistic trigger, e.g. “after”). In addition, only the trigger word must be annotated with the SNOMED CT concept. Section 5 explains that a relation must be drawn starting from the trigger word.

Temporality	Trigger	SNOMED CT	Example
Anteriority	before, before that, since, ...	SCTID: 272113006 Before values (qualifier value)	[Before] the surgery, an ECG was performed.
Simultaneity	during, meanwhile, when, ...	SCTID: 272114000 During values (qualifier value)	[During] the examination, the patient jumped up.
Posteriority	after, afterwards, ...	SCTID: 288563008 After values (qualifier value)	[After] the catheter was removed, we performed further examinations.

Table 4: Specific concepts for anteriority, simultaneity, and posteriority.

If a treatment is planned, the concept “SCTID: 397943006 | Planned (qualifier value)” must additionally be annotated. As illustrated in example (51), the concept can be annotated via trigger words such as “in”.

- (51) Die [**Dialyse**](a.) findet [**in**](b.) [**4**](c.) [**Wochen**](d.) statt.
- SCTID: 108241001 | Dialysis procedure (procedure)
 - SCTID: 397943006 | Planned (qualifier value)
 - (4.0)
 - SCTID: 258705008 | week (qualifier value)
- Die Dialyse findet in 4 Wochen statt.
the dialysis takes in 4 weeks place
‘The dialysis will take place in four weeks.’

3.3.3.2 Quantities and numeric base type

Quantities include all *pure* numerical values, mostly in connection with observations and measurements, in the texts. In general, numerical values and linguistic expressions of these are annotated in INCEpTION without selecting a specific SNOMED CT concept. Instead, their value is entered as a decimal number in the `literal` field (see (52)-(55)).

- (52) Wir geben [**1**](a.) mg.
- (1.0)
Wir geben 1 mg.
we give 1 mg
‘We administer 1 mg.’

- (53) Laut Patient bestehen die Sehstörungen seit [**drei**](a.) Wochen und [**6**](b.) Tagen.
- (**3.0**)
 - (**6.0**)
 Laut Patient bestehen die Sehstörungen seit drei Wochen
 according.to patient exist the visual.disturbances since three weeks
 und 6 Tagen.
 and 6 days
 ‘According to the patient, the visual disturbances have existed for three weeks and six days.’
- (54) Der [**Durchschnitt**](a.) der [**Herzfrequenz**](b.) betrug [**50**](c.) bpm.
- SCTID: 255586005 | Mean (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 364075005 | Heart rate (observable entity)
 - (**50.0**)
 Der Durchschnitt der Herzfrequenz betrug 50 bpm.
 the average of.the heart.rate amounted.to 50 bpm
 ‘The average heart rate was 50 bpm.’
- (55) [[**RR**](a.)](b.) in Ruhe [**140**](c.)/[**80**](d.) mmHg.
- SCTID: 271649006 | Systolic blood pressure (observable entity)
 - SCTID: 271650006 | Diastolic blood pressure (observable entity)
 - 140.0**
 - 80.0**
 RR in Ruhe 140 / 80 mmHg.
 blood.pressure in rest 140 / 80 mmHg
 ‘Blood pressure at rest 140/80 mmHg.’

An exception is ordinal-scaled numerical values (e.g. “first” or “1st”). Ordinal values should be annotated with specific SNOMED CT codes of the hierarchy “SCTID: 272070003 | Ordinal number (qualifier value)” (see (56)).

- (56) Krankheitsstadium im [**1.**](a.) Zyklus.
- SCTID: 255216001 | First (qualifier value)
 Krankheitsstadium im 1. Zyklus.
 disease.stage in.the first cycle
 ‘Disease stage in the first cycle.’

3.3.3.3 Units

This category includes all possible information on units, which should generally be annotated as **Unit of measure** or its child concepts (see (57)). Units that occur together should also be annotated as such (see (58)).

- (57) RR in Ruhe 140/80 [**mmHg**](**a.**).
- a. SCTID: 259018001 | Millimeter of mercury (qualifier value)
RR in Ruhe 140 / 80 mmHg.
blood.pressure in rest 140 / 80 mmHg
'Blood pressure at rest 140/80 mmHg.'
- (58) Wir geben 10 [**mmol/L**](**a.**).
- a. SCTID: 258813002 | Millimole/liter (qualifier value)
Wir geben 10 mmol/L.
we give 10 mmol/L
'We administer 10 mmol/L.'

3.3.3.4 Comparatives

It can happen that lateralities or values are related and *compared*. In such cases, inequality symbols may also be used. Here, confusion can arise between the *Mathematical symbols* under the concept “SCTID: 276135000 | Mathematical sign (qualifier value)” and the *Topographic qualifiers* under the concept “SCTID: 106233006 | Topographical modifier (qualifier value)” (e.g. “SCTID: 276139006 | Less-than symbol < (qualifier value)” vs. “SCTID: 351726001 | Below (qualifier value)”). For inequality symbols between values, the concepts of the *Mathematical symbols* and not the *Topographic qualifiers* are always to be selected (see Ex. (59)). The latter are only to be selected if the statements are actually spatial-topological statements (see Ex. (60), which is axiomatically linked to ‘SCTID: 351726001 | Below (qualifier value)’).

(59) [KÖF](a.) [<](b.) [1.3](c.).

- a. SCTID: 251010005 | Cardiac valve area (observable entity)
- b. SCTID: 276139006 | Less-than symbol < (qualifier value)
- c. (1.3)

KÖF < 1.3.
cardiac.valve.area less.than 1.3
‘Cardiac valve area < 1.3.’

(60) Pt. kommt mit [amputierter linker Extremität unterhalb des Knies](a.).

- a. SCTID: 816116009 | Amputated left lower limb below knee (finding)

Pt. kommt mit amputierter linker Extremität unterhalb des Knies.
patient comes with amputated left limb below the knee
‘The patient presents with an amputated left limb below the knee.’

However, if not only an inequality relation but also an explicit reference to a *reference value* is established in a text, a concept under the *reference range interpretation values* (“SCTID: 442705008 | Reference range interpretation value (qualifier value)”) is to be selected (see Ex. (61), which is axiomatically linked to “SCTID: 281300000 | Below reference range (qualifier value)”).

(61) [Laktosegehalt unter Referenzwert](a.).

- a. SCTID: 124001001 | Lactose below reference range (finding)

Laktosegehalt unter Referenzwert.
lactose.content below reference.value
‘Lactose content below reference value.’

3.3.3.5 Negation and factuality

Negation: Every type of negation is annotated with the concept “SCTID: 410516002 | Known absent (qualifier value)”. This applies to all occurrences of negation particles (see (62)). Adjacent negation and factuality markers should be annotated jointly with the concept they modify. Of course only if such a precoordinated concept exists in SNOMED

CT. Concepts that are already negated do not require a separate negation annotation (cf. (63)).

- (62) Es ist [**keine**](a.) weitere Diagnose möglich.
a. SCTID: 410516002 | Known absent (qualifier value)
Es ist keine weitere Diagnose möglich.
it is no further diagnosis possible
'No further diagnosis is possible.'

- (63) Wir können [**keine Lähmung**](a.) feststellen.
a. SCTID: 274811005 | Paralysis absent (finding)
Wir können keine Lähmung feststellen.
we can no paralysis detect
'We cannot detect paralysis.'

Factuality: differential diagnoses: A differential diagnosis lists the diseases with almost identical symptoms to the suspected diagnosis. The differential diagnoses themselves are to be annotated with their respective SNOMED CT concepts. A *trigger* word that indicates the existence of a differential diagnosis (e.g. “DD” in (64)) is to be annotated with “SCTID: 47965005 | Differential diagnosis (contextual qualifier) (qualifier value)”.

- (64) Der Patient hat [**Rheuma**](a.), [**DD**](b.): [**Psoriasisarthritis**](c..
a. SCTID: 396332003 | Rheumatism (disorder
b. SCTID: 47965005 | Differential diagnosis (contextual qualifier) (qualifier value)
c. SCTID: 156370009 | Psoriatic arthritis (disorder)
Der Patient hat Rheuma DD Psoriasisarthritis.
the patient has rheumatism differential.diagnosis psoriatic.arthritis
'The patient has rheumatism, differential diagnosis: psoriatic arthritis.'

Factuality: assertion certainty: In annotation, it is generally assumed that concepts are *neither negated nor otherwise modified in their factuality*, unless the text permits explicit contrary conclusions. Tab. 5 illustrates the SNOMED CT concepts to be annotated for factuality triggers concerning assertion certainty (= (un)certainty of statements) in the text. The table is arranged like a scale: The extremes are associated with the highest certainty, once in the positive sense (e.g. a disease is *confirmed*) and once in the negative sense (e.g. a disease is *excluded*). In between, there is a *positive* (e.g. “probably”) and a *negative* level (e.g. “unlikely”) of uncertainty. In the default case, i.e. the assumption that something is present, no trigger word should be annotated. Example (65) shows how factualities can also be expressed.

- (65) [Laut Patient](a.) bestand [Divertikulitis](b.).
- a. SCTID: 410592001 | Probably present (qualifier value)
 - b. SCTID: 307496006 | Diverticulitis (disorder)
- Laut Patient bestand Divertikulitis.
 according.to patient existed diverticulitis
 ‘According to the patient, diverticulitis was present.’

Certainty of an assertion	Factuality trigger	SNOMED CT	Text example
Very certain (+)	Status post (s.p.), condition after, confirmed, unequivocal, doubtless, certain, known, ...	SCTID: 410605003 Confirmed present (qualifier value)	Tonsil stone could be [confirmed](.).
Certain (+) <i>DEFAULT</i>	be present, exist, ...	∅	Tonsil stone is present.
Less certain (+)	suspicion of, probable, certainly, with high probability, tends to, presumably, possibly, potentially, if applicable, subjunctive, ...	SCTID: 410592001 Probably present (qualifier value)	Tonsil stone is [probably](.) present.
Less certain (-)	unlikely, unexpected, subjunctive, ...	SCTID: 410593006 Probably not present (qualifier value)	A tonsil stone is [unlikely](.).
(Very) certain (-)	exclusion of, excluded, refuted, no indication of, no evidence of, ...	SCTID: 410516002 Known absent (qualifier value)	The tonsil stone diagnosis was [refuted](.).

Table 5: GeMTeX factuality scale (certainty) according to SNOMED CT

If a negation particle is a direct neighbor of a factuality marker, a joint concept can be used, see (66). Compounds, which often occur in German, frequently force a stacked annotation, see (67).

- (66) Ein Tonsillenstein ist [**nicht wahrscheinlich**](a.).
- a. SCTID: 410593006 | Probably not present (qualifier value)
- Ein Tonsillenstein ist nicht wahrscheinlich.
 a tonsil.stone is not likely
 ‘A tonsil stone is not likely.’

- (67) Es besteht [[**Leukämieverdacht**](a.)](b.).
- SCTID: 93143009 | Leukemia, disease (disorder)
 - SCTID: 410592001 | Probably present (qualifier value)
- Es besteht Leukämieverdacht.
it exists leukemia.suspicion
‘There is suspicion of leukemia.’

Recommendations and indications: Another factuality is the *recommendation*. If a procedure has been recommended in the text, it can be annotated either as *recommended* or as *indicated*. While the former refers to guideline recommendations, the latter means medically necessary recommendations (see Tab. 6). The rule is: In principle, decisions and treatments are to be classified as medically necessary. Only in explicit mentions of guidelines or similar should the concept “SCTID: 897015005 | Recommended (qualifier value)” be used.

Concept	Meaning/ use	Text example
SCTID: 410535002 Indicated (qualifier value)	DEFAULT: A treatment is medically indicated	The treatment is [recommended due to the clinical condition](.).
SCTID: 897015005 Recommended (qualifier value)	A treatment is recommended by best practices or guidelines, but not mandatory (<i>Use only if guidelines or best practices or similar are explicitly mentioned.</i>)	Influenza vaccination is [recommended by STIKO](.).

Table 6: Factuality markers for recommendation & planning.

Past clinical states or procedures: Diseases or procedures can be marked as *past* or *over* in clinical documents, or they may simply already lie somewhat in the past. A classic trigger word for this is “condition after”. In such a case, the trigger word is annotated with “SCTID: 410513005 | In the past (qualifier value)” (see (68)).

- (68) [[**Z.n.**](a.)](b.) [**Vasektomie**](c.): [**Unauffällig**](d.).
- SCTID: 410605003 | Confirmed present (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 410513005 | In the past (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 22523008 | Vasectomy (procedure)
 - SCTID: 17621005 | Normal (qualifier value)
- Z.n. Vasektomie unauffällig.
status.after vasectomy unremarkable
‘Status post vasectomy: unremarkable.’

Note

Child concepts of “SCTID: 243796009 | Situation with explicit context (situation)” are excluded from GeMTeX annotation and should not be used.

3.3.3.6 Further Qualifier concepts

There are numerous other Qualifiers in SNOMED CT that may be used in annotation. An example of such a category is “SCTID: 272099008 | Descriptor (qualifier value)”, which is divided into numerous child concepts. Under this category, for example, the concept “SCTID: 14803004 | Transitory (qualifier value)” can be found, which describes a temporally limited occurrence of a Finding, as in (69); or the concept “SCTID: 281302008 | Above reference range (qualifier value)”, which usually describes a measured value that is explicitly above a reference value (see (70)). In general, preference should be given to those Qualifier concepts that themselves occur within SNOMED CT concept definitions. This can be illustrated using the “References” tab in the SNOMED CT International SNOMED CT Browser.

- (69) Es war ein [**passagerer**](a.) Diabetes Mellitus.
- a. SCTID: 14803004 | Transitory (qualifier value)
Es war ein passagerer Diabetes Mellitus.
it was a transient diabetes mellitus
'It was transient diabetes mellitus.'
- (70) Messung [**erhöht**](a.).
- a. SCTID: 281302008 | Above reference range (qualifier value)
Messung erhöht.
measurement elevated
'Measurement elevated.'

3.4 Familial diseases

It may happen that familial (previous) diseases are listed in a clinical document. In order to clearly distinguish these from the patient’s diseases, they must be marked separately in the texts.

In GeMTeX, persons should generally not be annotated. In the family history, however, we make an exception and annotate family members if they are mentioned in connection with a disease or treatment. For this, SNOMED CT concepts under “SCTID: 303071001 | Person in the family (person)” should be used (see (71)). If no person is mentioned, but it is nevertheless clear that familial diseases are involved, the generic concept just mentioned, “SCTID: 303071001 | Person in the family (person)”, is to be used (see (72)). Chapter 5 illustrates that the disease and its family affiliation should be connected by a relation.

- (71) Der **[Vater](a.)** des Betroffenen litt unter einem **[Katarakt li.](b.)**.
- a. SCTID: 9947008 | Natural father (person)
 - b. SCTID: 816119002 | Cataract of left eye (disorder)
- Der Vater des Betroffenen litt unter einem Katarakt li.
the father of.the affected.person suffered under a cataract left
‘The affected person’s father suffered from a left cataract.’
- (72) **[In der Familie](a.)** der Betroffenen gab es einen Fall von **[Knochenmarkskrebs.](b.)**.
- a. SCTID: 303071001 | Person in the family (person)
 - b. SCTID: 445738007 | Myelodysplastic/myeloproliferative disease (disorder)
- In der Familie der Betroffenen gab es einen Fall von
in the family of.the affected.person gave it a case of
Knochenmarkskrebs.
bone.marrow.cancer
‘In the affected person’s family, there was a case of bone marrow cancer.’

Note

In family history as well, child concepts of “SCTID: 243796009 | Situation with explicit context (situation)” are not to be used for annotation.

4 The No-Human layer: Marking areas annotated exclusively by machine

In order to keep the time required for manual annotation work low, especially non-narrative areas of a clinical text are excluded from annotation. The following areas should not be annotated:

- Long lists of laboratory values
- Dosage or administration information for medications
- Long lists of medications
- Tables
- ICD codes
- Document structures / section headings (e.g. the heading “Diagnosis”)

The annotators have the choice between two procedures: (A) They can delete existing preannotation or (B) draw the so-called No-Human layer over the relevant areas. Both variants are equivalent.

Variant A: Deletion of preannotation: If the above-mentioned parts of a document are preannotated, the relevant preannotation can be deleted. It must be ensured that all concepts have been removed from the respective text passage.

Variant B: The No-Human layer: An alternative to deletion is drawing the No-Human layer in order to clearly mark that an area was not checked by humans. In INCEpTION, for this purpose, one must first switch in the drop-down menu at the top right from the layer `Concept` to the layer `No_Human` (see Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Selection of the `No_Human` layer in INCEpTION.

It is recommended to use the variants efficiently depending on the situation: For example, it can make sense to simply delete a preannotation of an ICD-10 code, since this can be done in a few clicks. A long list of laboratory values, on the other hand, can be a good case for the No-Human layer.

5 Adding relations

In addition to the introduced **concepts**, which are annotated over spans in the text and grounded to SNOMED CT, these should also be connected to one another by **relations** in the semantic annotation of GeMTeX. There is only one generic type of relation, represented here as $\overrightarrow{r}_{x \in D_e, y \in D_e}$, which has no labels and fundamentally connects only two annotates x and y with each other. In the following, the basic rules of semantic relation annotation for GeMTeX are explained.

Note

In the following sections, a respectively *preferred relation direction* is specified. This should generally be followed. If this becomes too complex, relations can also be drawn from left to right by default.

5.1 Semantic relations

The most basic condition for drawing a relation between two annotates in the text is semantic coherence. Two annotates must be semantically connected, so that a relation should be drawn. Semantic coherence here means that two or more concepts must necessarily be interpreted jointly in order to understand the meaning behind the actual statement in the document.

Example (73) illustrates such a case: Since there is no joint concept for a transient ischemic attack of the left hemisphere, the concepts must be annotated separately. To enable complete interpretation of the finding, the two concepts are connected by a relation. The preferred direction of the relation goes from Core concepts to Modifier or Qualifier concepts and from Modifier concepts to Qualifier concepts. If two concepts of equal rank are connected, the relation direction should be chosen from left to right.

- (73) Wir berichten über eine [linkshemisphärielle](a.) [TIA](b.).
- SCTID: 72792008 | Left cerebral hemisphere structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 266257000 | Transient ischemic attack (disorder)

Wir berichten über eine linkshemisphärielle TIA.

we report about a left.hemispheric TIA

‘We report a left-hemispheric TIA.’

5.2 Relations in familial diseases

If diseases occur not in the patient, but in family members, the disease must be connected to the corresponding family member. As shown in (74), the preferred relation direction starts from the person and points to the disease.

- $\overrightarrow{r}_{a,b}$
- (74) Der [**Vater**](a.) des Betroffenen litt unter einem [**Katarakt li.**](b.).
- a. SCTID: 9947008 | Natural father (person)
 - b. SCTID: 816119002 | Cataract of left eye (disorder)
- Der Vater des Betroffenen litt unter einem Katarakt li.
the father of.the affected.person suffered under a cataract left
'The affected person's father suffered from a left cataract.'

5.3 Causal relations

If two concepts stand in an obvious causal relation to each other, a relation must be drawn between the two. An obvious causal relation is present if causality is explicitly expressed, e.g. by a causal conjunction such as “because” or “due to”. In addition, one of the concepts must be the cause of the other concept. The preferred relation direction starts at the cause and ends at the result.

- $\overrightarrow{r}_{b,a}$
- (75) Pt. aufgenommen mit [**akutem Myokardinfarkt**](a.) wg. [**arteriosklerot. Gefäßerkr.**](b.).
- a. SCTID: 57054005 | Acute myocardial infarction (disorder)
 - b. SCTID: 72092001 | Arteriosclerotic vascular disease (disorder)
- Pt. aufgenommen mit akutem Myokardinfarkt wg.
patient admitted with acute myocardial.infarction because.of
arteriosklerot. Gefäßerkr.
arteriosclerotic vascular.disease
'Patient admitted with acute myocardial infarction due to arteriosclerotic vascular disease.'

5.4 Anaphoric relations

Anaphors should always be connected to the concept to which they refer. Example (76) shows that both spans were annotated with the same SNOMED CT concept. In addition, they should be connected by a relation. The preferred relation direction goes from the concrete mention to the anaphoric reference.

$\vec{r}_{a,b}$

(76) Pt. wurde [**Voltaren**](a.) verschrieben. Pt. hat [**das Medikament**](a.) nicht genommen.

a. SCTID: 775563008 | Product containing only diclofenac (medicinal product)

Pt. wurde Voltaren verschrieben. Pt. hat das Medikament nicht
patient was Voltaren prescribed patient has the medication not

genommen.

taken

‘The patient was prescribed Voltaren. The patient did not take the medication.’

5.5 Measured-value relations

In the context of *Observable Entities*, measured values and units often occur. These must always be brought into a relation with one another. The relation should be directed from the Observable Entity to the measured value and from the measured value to the unit (cf. (77)). If one of the three features is not present in the text, a relation must nevertheless be drawn between the remaining two features.

 $\vec{r}_{a,b}$ $\vec{r}_{b,c}$

(77) Die [**Herzfrequenz**](a.) liegt bei [**55**](b.) [**bpm**](c.).

a. SCTID: 364075005 | Heart rate (observable entity)

b. (**55.0**)

c. SCTID: 258983007 | Beats/minute (qualifier value)

Die Herzfrequenz liegt bei 55 bpm.

the heart.rate lies at 55 bpm

‘The heart rate is 55 bpm.’

5.6 Boundary relations

As soon as a value range or a span between two measured values, dates, or even degrees is given, a relation must be drawn from the lower boundary to the upper boundary (see Ex. (78) and (79)).

(78) Der Patient war von **[23.10.](a.)-[31.10.21](b.)** in stationärer Behandlung.

a. SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value) **(2021-10-23)**

b. SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value) **(2021-10-31)**

Der Patient war von 23.10. bis 31.10.21 in stationärer Behandlung.

the patient was from 23.10. to 31.10.21 in inpatient treatment

‘The patient was in inpatient treatment from 23.10. to 31.10.21.’

(79) Sie erlitt **[[Verbrennungen 2.](a.) - 3. Grades](b.)**.

a. SCTID: 403191005 | Partial thickness burn (disorder)

b. SCTID: 403192003 | Full thickness burn (disorder)

Sie erlitt Verbrennungen 2. - 3. Grades.

she suffered burns second to third degree

‘She suffered second- to third-degree burns.’

If a measured-value relation and the boundary relation coincide, the complexity is to be reduced as follows: The first relation goes from the Observable Entity to the lower boundary. The second relation points from the lower to the upper boundary. The last relation points from the upper boundary to the unit (cf. (80)).

- (80) [Syst. Blutdr.](a.) höchstens zwischen [146](b.) und [120](c.) [mmHg](d.).
- SCTID: 271649006 | Systolic blood pressure (observable entity)
 - 146.0
 - 120.0
 - SCTID: 259018001 | Millimeter of mercury (qualifier value)
- Syst. Blutdr. höchstens zwischen 146 und 120 mmHg.
systolic blood.pressure at.most between 146 and 120 mmHg
‘Systolic blood pressure at most between 146 and 120 mmHg.’

5.7 Coordination relations

In Chapter 2, (syntactic) coordination is addressed in the context of Maxim II. The rule defines that coordinated units must be annotated separately from one another and from the coordination predicate to which they refer. This is also shown in example (21), reproduced here in full annotation as (81).

It becomes clear that the coordinated units “head” and “ears” are annotated separately from one another, as is the coordination predicate “third-degree burned”, which further specifies the situation of the coordinated units. A relation should now be drawn from the coordination predicate to the two coordinated units - it is not necessary to draw a relation between the coordinated units.

- (81) [Kopf](a.) und [Ohren](b.) [drittgradig verbrannt](c.).
- SCTID: 69536005 | Head structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 117590005 | Ear structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 1403192003 | Full thickness burn (disorder)
- Kopf und Ohren drittgradig verbrannt.
head and ears third.degree burned
‘Head and ears third-degree burned.’

5.8 Factuality relations

Factuality indicators and negation particles modify or invert the semantics of certain expressions and therefore have massive effects on the correct interpretation of statements. To account for this contribution, a relation must be drawn from factuality or negation particles to every annotate that is modified by them. If several annotates are affected by the modification, a relation must be drawn to each of these annotates. Example (82) illustrates the annotation of factualities.

- (82) [**Wahrscheinlich**](a.) liegt eine [**Läsion im Auge**](b.) vor.
- SCTID: 410592001 | Probably present (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 301905003 | Lesion of eye (disorder)
- Wahrscheinlich liegt eine Läsion im Auge vor.
 probably lies a lesion in.the eye PRT
 ‘There is probably a lesion in the eye.’

In (83), a case is illustrated where a negation modifies several concepts: The sentence states that neither intracranial nor intracerebral traumas are present, without specifying whether further traumas are present. Consequently, the negation here modifies the two localization specifications, which in turn further specify the traumas. Thus, one relation each must be drawn from “no” to the two localization specifications. Since the two localization specifications are coordinated with the concept of traumas, one relation each must also be drawn from “traumas” to the two localities.

- (83) [**Kopf-CT**](a.) ergab [**keine**](b.) [**intrakr.**](c.) oder [**intracer.**](d.) [**Traumata**](e.).
- SCTID: 303653007 | Computed tomography of head (procedure)
 - SCTID: 410516002 | Known absent (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 128319008 | Intracranial structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 12738006 | Brain structure (body structure)
 - SCTID: 417746004 | Traumatic injury (disorder)
- Kopf-CT ergab keine intrakr. oder intracer. Traumata.
 head.CT yielded no intracranial or intracerebral traumas
 ‘The head CT showed no intracranial or intracerebral traumas.’

5.9 Temporal relations

Temporal relations can only be triggered by a trigger word that expresses anteriority, simultaneity, or posteriority (cf. Section 3.3.3.1). If such a trigger word occurs (e.g. “before” in Ex. (84)), a relation chain must be formed according to the following principle:

- ANTERIOR(Concept A, Concept B) and Concept A takes place before Concept B.
- SIMULTANEOUS(Concept A, Concept B) and Concept A occurs before Concept B in the text.
- POSTERIOR(Concept A, Concept B) and Concept A takes place after Concept B.

In the case of anteriority, a relation must first be drawn from the trigger word to the concept taking place earlier. Subsequently, a relation must be drawn from the earlier to the later concept. Posteriority behaves analogously (i.e.: The trigger points to the concept taking place later, which in turn points to the concept taking place earlier). In

simultaneity, the preferred relation direction corresponds to the reading direction (from left to right). One example each of the temporal relation is shown in the following examples (84), (85), and (86).

(84) [Vor](a.) der [OP](b.) wird ein [ambulantes EKG](c.) durchgeführt.

- a. SCTID: 272113006 | Before values (qualifier value)
- b. SCTID: 5387713003 | Surgical procedure (procedure)
- c. SCTID: 164850009 | Ambulatory electrocardiogram (procedure)

Vor der OP wird ein ambulantes EKG durchgeführt.
 before the surgery is an ambulatory ECG performed
 ‘Before the surgery, an ambulatory ECG is performed.’

(85) [Nach](a.) der [OP](b.) wird ein [ambulantes EKG](c.) durchgeführt.

- a. SCTID: 288563008 | After values (qualifier value)
- b. SCTID: 5387713003 | Surgical procedure (procedure)
- c. SCTID: 164850009 | Ambulatory electrocardiogram (procedure)

Nach der OP wird ein ambulantes EKG durchgeführt.
 after the surgery is an ambulatory ECG performed
 ‘After the surgery, an ambulatory ECG is performed.’

Example (86) also shows how factuality triggers are to be integrated into such a relation chain: As described in Section 5.8, the factuality trigger is not integrated into the existing chain. Only a relation between the trigger word and the concept to be modified is drawn.

(86) [Während](a.) der [OP](b.) kam es zu [keinen](c.) [Komplikationen](d.).

- a. SCTID: 288563008 | After values (qualifier value)
- b. SCTID: 5387713003 | Surgical procedure (procedure)
- c. SCTID: 410516002 | Known absent (qualifier value)
- d. SCTID: 738778005 | Intraoperative complication (disorder)

Während der OP kam es zu keinen Komplikationen.
 during the surgery came it to no complications
 ‘During the surgery, there were no complications.’

6 Annotation pragmatics: Complete example annotations and borderline cases

This section provides examples of fully annotated texts. The examples differ in complexity, length, and concept density. The first example (87) shows the annotation of a longer text span that is nevertheless *meaningful* and connected by *adjacent linguistic units*.

- (87) Die Patientin litt unter [**symptomatischem Anfallsleiden**](a.).
a. SCTID: 230381009 | Focal epilepsy (disorder)
Die Patientin litt unter symptomatischem Anfallsleiden.
the patient.F suffered under symptomatic seizure.disorder
‘The patient suffered from symptomatic seizure disorder.’

The example sentences (88) and (89) illustrate the rules of Maxim II very clearly: (88) shows a sentence that contains completely adjacent tokens that form a meaningful unit and can therefore be annotated as one total span with a precise SNOMED CT concept.

The sentence in (89) contains two pitfalls: The span contains an area with two boundaries¹⁰. Therefore, the two boundaries must first be connected by a relation. Second, we note that the ‘ear’ is connected to the rest of the sentence by a copular verb ‘was’. Thus, we annotate the entire sentence with the SNOMED CT concept “SCTID: 9065001 | Burn of ear (disorder)” and treat the burn-degree specifications as insertions (cf. Maxim II, Chapter 2).

- (88) Das [**Ohr war im II. Grad verbrannt**](a.).
a. 269233004 | Superficial partial thickness burn of ear (disorder)
Das Ohr war im II. Grad verbrannt.
the ear was in.the second degree burned
‘The ear was burned to the second degree.’

¹⁰Note: Burn degrees are not a real value range, since they are only categorically ordered. Therefore, this is also not annotated with numerical values, but with their actual meanings as SNOMED CT concepts. Since a range is linguistically indicated by the word “to”, the boundary rule applies here.

(89) Das [Ohr war im [II.](b.) bis [III. Grad](c.) verbrannt](a.).

- a. SCTID: 39065001 | Burn of ear (disorder)
- b. SCTID: 403191005 | Partial thickness burn (disorder)
- c. SCTID: 403192003 | Full thickness burn (disorder)

Das Ohr war im II. bis III. Grad verbrannt.
 the ear was in.the second to third degree burned

‘The ear was burned to the second to third degree.’

The example in (90) contains an enumeration of medical procedures. The date “01/99” does not have to be integrated into a relation. The localization specification “dorsum of left hand” is the coordination predicate of the two coordinated units “VAC change” and “debridement”. According to the coordination rule, both coordinated units must be connected to their coordination predicate (preferred: starting from the coordination predicate).

(90) [1/99](a.): [VAC-Wechsel](b.) u. [Debridement](c.) [li. Handrücken](d.).

- a. SCTID: 410672004 | Date property (qualifier value) (1999-01-xx)
- b. SCTID: 1217562000 | Replacement of negative pressure wound dressing (procedure)
- c. SCTID: 36777000 | Debridement (procedure)
- d. SCTID: 789218009 | Structure of dorsum of left hand (body structure)

1/99 VAC-Wechsel u. Debridement li. Handrücken.

1/99 VAC.change and debridement left dorsum.of.hand

‘1/99: VAC change and debridement on the dorsum of the left hand.’

The following example illustrates how to deal with differential diagnoses. The trigger word “DD” is annotated with the SNOMED CT concept proposed in the guideline. The original diagnosis and the differential diagnosis, “rheumatism” and “psoriatic arthritis”, are annotated with the respectively suitable concepts. The trigger word points to the element it modifies, here therefore “psoriatic arthritis”.

- (91) Der Patient hat [**Rheuma**(a.)], [**DD**](b.): [**Psoriasisarthritis**](c.).
- SCTID: 396332003 | Rheumatism (disorder)
 - SCTID: 47965005 | Differential diagnosis (contextual qualifier) (qualifier value)
 - SCTID: 156370009 | Psoriatic arthritis (disorder)
- Der Patient hat Rheuma DD Psoriasisarthritis.
the patient has rheumatism differential.diagnosis psoriatic.arthritis
‘The patient has rheumatism, differential diagnosis: psoriatic arthritis.’

In (92), another factuality example is illustrated, but with relation direction against the reading direction. The relation always points from a factuality indicator to the annotate that is modified.

- (92) Ein [**erhöhtes Schlaganfallrisiko**](b.) wird [**vermutet**](b.).
- SCTID: 866240007 | At increased risk of cerebrovascular accident (finding)
 - SCTID: 410592001 | Probably present (qualifier value)
- Ein erhöhtes Schlaganfallrisiko wird vermutet.
an increased stroke.risk is suspected
‘An increased risk of stroke is suspected.’

An anaphoric construction can be observed in (93): “blood pressure values” and “systolic” refer to the same concept “SCTID: 271649006 | Systolic blood pressure (observable entity)” and are therefore connected by a relation. Furthermore, a relation goes from the first instance of the anaphor “blood pressure values” to the lower boundary of the actually measured values “170”. Due to the boundary rule, the latter concept points to the upper boundary “180”, which in turn is directed to the unit “mmHg”.

(93) [Blutdruckwerte](a.) zwischen [170](b.) und [180](c.) [mmHg](d.) [systolisch](a.).

a. SCTID: 271649006 | Systolic blood pressure (observable entity)

b. **(170.0)**

c. **(180.0)**

d. SCTID: 259018001 | Millimeter of mercury (qualifier value)

Blutdruckwerte zwischen 170 und 180 mmHg systolisch.

blood.pressure.values between 170 and 180 mmHg systolic

‘Blood pressure values between 170 and 180 mmHg systolic.’

7 Curation notes

This chapter is intended for the locally operating curation personnel and lists short notes on the curation of semantic annotation in GeMTeX.

In principle, semantic annotation follows the **two-person principle**. This means that a student assistant annotates each document with the help of automatic preannotation and the ID Recommender. This is in contrast to the four-person principle practiced in de-identification. In order to measure the alignment of the annotators and to regularly evaluate the correctness and rule-based nature of the semantic annotations, 1 % of the documents of a batch should be annotated *by all annotators*. These should be checked for inter-annotator agreement values and semantic correctness. In addition, it is advisable to discuss text examples jointly in the group of annotators. In most cases, the assistants bring medical knowledge and the curators bring technical-organizational knowledge. Experience shows that ambiguities and gray areas can be resolved well in this way. In particularly tricky cases, it is recommended to extend the debate to the cross-site curation meeting.